

Nurses Enhancing Care Coordination Among Children In Foster Care

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Background and Significance

- Up to 80% of children entering FC have unmet needs for medical and dental care
- LAC DCFS goal is 90% compliance rate for medical and dental exams, yet performance is less than 60% and 30%, respectively
- Better care coordination between Social Workers (SWs), Public Health Nurses (PHNs), Caregivers (CGs), and Healthcare Providers can help improve health status for children and youth in FC

Purpose

- Improve care coordination for foster care (FC) children and youth to increase medical and dental examination rates and thus, health status of these youth

Methods

- IRB approval by involved agencies
- PHN and SW focus groups on perceptions of care coordination
- Revision of PHN roles and responsibilities policy and procedure with subsequent training
- Pre-post project design to compare PHN consultations and communications and medical/dental compliance rates

Qualitative Findings

- System and process barriers
- Inadequate communication between PHN/SWs
- Need for education and training on a clear defined PHN care coordination practice guideline
- Heavy workloads for PHNs and SWs

Conceptual Framework

Conclusion

- High commitment of PHNs and SWs to health of kids in foster care; ongoing work on system barriers may further improve health compliance rates
- Increased number of completed PHN consults and communication with increased medical exam compliance and 1% decreased dental compliance
- System issues remained

Limitations

- PHN/child ratio was above State-recommended levels during project
- PHNs did not have ready access to medical files and the Orchid system, thus creating additional time demands

Recommendations

- Resolve issues with PHN access to medical files to improve timely reporting
- Train clerks and human service aides to better assist with care coordination activities such as obtaining medical and dental records from caregivers or Healthcare Providers
- Maintain new care coordination policy; continue to track relationship between PHN consults/communications and medical/dental compliance rate
- Maintain communication and collaboration among PHNs and SWs and supervisory staff, including monthly reports on compliance rates

Quantitative Findings

